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ABONARE

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A Scientifically Acceptable Mechanism for the Reincarnation Process of the Self

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Rezumat

Propunem o abordare paradigmatică nouă a realității perceptibile în ansamblu, cu aplicație specifică dinamicii ADN-ului ghidat de informație, conducând la o configurație genomică triadică, care găzduiește, pe lângă moștenirea ereditară parentală, o matrice de ghidare extrem de complexă de origine transcendențială, capabilă să controleze modul specific în care se realizează sinteza proteinelor. „Genomul Sufletului” propriu al Sinelui, care transcende bariera interdimensională a energiei punctului zero, se cuplează cu configurația energetică guvernată cuantică a zigotului prin intermediul benzilor rezonante de efecte de suprapunere a energiei subtile în momentul fertilizării, declanșate de o punte biofotonică legată de microexplozia de zinc. . Astfel, parametrii secundari unici de torsiune din catenele ADN determină modul în care este citit șablonul de bază generator de proteine, furnizând particularitățile psiho-cognitive ale noii entități de-a lungul vectorilor de dezvoltare intenționați.

Cuvinte cheie: reîncarnare, sine, suflet, subcuantic, energie subtilă, ADN, microexplozie de zinc.

Abstract

We propose a novel paradigmatic approach to sentient reality as a whole, with specific application to Information-guided DNA dynamics, leading to a triadic genomic configuration, which accommodates besides the parental hereditary legacy, a transcendental originating highly complex guiding matrix able to control the specific way the protein-synthesis is performed. The Self's own "Soul Genome", transcending the zero point energy interdimensional barrier, couples to the zygote's quantum-governed energetic configuration by way of resonant bands of subtle energy superposition effects at the instance of fertilization, triggered by a Zinc-spark related

biophotonic bridge. Thus, unique secondary torsion parameters in the DNA strands determine the way the basic protein-generating template is read, supplying the new entity's psycho-cognitive particularities along purposeful developmental vectors.

Keywords: Reincarnation, self, soul, subquantum, subtle energy, DNA, Zinc spark.

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1. Introduction

Our working hypothesis is derived from the Nobel-prize winner " Fractional Quantum Hall Effect" (1998), allowing for an infinite divisibility of Quanta as well as existence of elementary particles exhibiting fractional mass and charge values. At the bottom of this downward scaling of magnitudes, at the subquantum unit's level, Information (as an ontological prime brought on equal footing with matter and energy) couples to the space/time frame of reference. Any combinatorial configurations of this unit, upscaled through increasing complexity variants, will preserve the aforementioned triadic aspect, allowing an Information-guided control, via subquantum vacuum fluctuations and divergences in the Quantum Potential, upon any conceivable variants of manifestation.

2. Consciousness Beyond the Death of the Physical Body

Subtle energy systems (S.E.) inside and between organized Information fields and only partly subject to space/time constraints, operate as specialized mediating networks coordinating biologically relevant vital functions. When coupled to conventional matter/energy events, behavioral patterns with semi-stable features may result (as in ectoplasmic materialization instances). S.E. variants have a hyperdimensional vortical nature. A basic similarity has been

suggested between S.E. forms and the superstring theory (Phillips, 1999). Important to keep in mind, that electromagnetic vibrations may stimulate resonant vibration patterns in S.E. fields.

S.E. fields emerge out of the Z.P.E. (Zero point energy) in order to enter transduction processes into quasi-physical variants, able to interact with classical field phenomena by energy interactions. According to W. Tiller (1993), magnetic vector potentials may bridge between the non-physical and physical domains. Very important to mention here, that photonic outbursts may couple to subtle energy spectra in selective resonant ways. An available etheric template, carrying implicate orders of informational essence, may couple to the zygote's EM polarization fluctuations, by a cascade-like resonant chain of harmonics, by way of S.Q. flux propagations. This process stands at the background of SQ genetic patternings, as a result of superluminal nonlinear photonic oscillation. The embryologic transcription process runs under coherent biphotonic regulation, in time-symmetric and time conversion conditions.

C. Trajna (1991) in his "psychotemporal wave" concept defines subjective time flow as a differential perception of the propagation velocity of psychic information signals vs. biological (neurotransmitted) ones. Brain's Quantum activity provides the time conversion of informational stuff operating beyond time, thus extending into extrasensory information dynamics. The event-modulating properties of information presets have at their background S.E. bands and vectors, responsible for non-neural information transfers.

In Cramer's (1986) transactional interpretation of Quantum Mechanics, besides the Quantum potential expressed in physical space/time, there is also a hidden time domain. In this domain, synchronous superposed causal vectors run in opposite directions. In other words, a physical entropic causal vector is paralleled by a coaxial Information one, which is a signal emitted by future deterministic presets of actualization, able to trigger a "probing act" that has to be issued by previous causal constellations. Between the couple of opposed informational vectors, a causal loop is formed in hidden time. The whole causal loop projects into our linear entropic timeline in null time (the "present" instant), implementing the quantum choice by the collapse of the Schrodinger function. Most remarkably, we may conclude that reality is not epiphenomenal to a random collapse of probability waves, but the other way around: the Schrodinger collapse instance occurs at specific points according to the reality to be implemented. Hidden time dynamics occurring in information fields implement informational enfolded control upon energetic phenomena at all levels. A time-reversed effect of retro causation gets also conceivable. It allows

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a guiding of the embryogenetic process by purposeful development vectors, which operate upon the etheric templates of morphogenetic fields. Such templates will grant the specific patterning of neural networks in the brain, the only organ able to work in a hyperdimensional frame of reference - being an entropy stabilizing system. This function ability of neural systems in the 5th dimension has been explained in mathematic terms by Togbey (2006), and experimentally proved by Walling & Hicks (2009).

Following the sequential increase of the dimensional correlates corresponding to specific attractors associated with progressive emergence from deep anesthesia, the authors were able to put in evidence some very interesting and highly meaningful correlations between brain function levels and their EEG-derived electromagnetic representations. The gamma ascent event at the EEG plot marks the instance of conscient activity, associated with specific neocortical dynamics especially in the frontal areas of the brain. This effect is associated to a chaotic attractor of high complexity derived from EEG analysis. This understanding clearly suggests that consciousness is no way a collective effect of conformational dynamics evolving at some lower hierarchic implication level. Of course, chemical energy patterns also have Information propagating efficiency, and unimpaired conformal functions of collective neural assemblies are required for up-scaled integrations of Qualia and provide meanings into the Self.

Our working hypothesis sharply shifts away from the current reductionist dogmas that see cognition merely as a result of pattern-generating effects of neural connectivity. Abstract functions exceed space-time constraints. Brain's efficiency manifests as an ideal anchorage system for connecting biological events to proactive conformally organized information fields, by way of holographic interactions.

Back in 2008, a most thought-provoking work has been published by Paul von Ward. His new notion introduced into the genetical language, the "Soul Genome", is pointing to a possible extension of the dual parental genetic heritage into a more complex genetic trad, including Informational configurations pertaining to the to-be-born entity itself, able to be injected into the total genetic setup and thus impacting the parental one by further modulations in the DNA biochemical maps in specific ways, in the fertilization context.

A mediating principle between basic chemistry and purposeful developing vectors toward biologically efficient blueprints is not content in the molecular map, it must be externally supplied

by quasi-material etheric templates - which build the grid structure of energy fields upon which the physical body growth.

At the instance of fertilization, a polar axis is created in the cell by its membrane's polarization. The electrical polarity and energy field of the polar axis are related to the process of first cell division. At the same instance, a third genetic input is injected into the system from outside the parental genetic legacy, in fact from outside our physical world. The couple of 23 chromosomal sets of classical genetics becomes not more than an efficient attractor for the incoming S.E. - mediated informational essence of the incarnating entity. The process clearly involves H. Stapp's "Quantum phase states" (2004; 2017).

Order is injected from nonlocal Information fields into the physical domains, resulting in guiding morphogenetic modulators at early embryogenetic stages.

For the descent of the Self into the parental supply of genetic attractors, a transgression of the Z.P.E. between the nonlocal, semi material subtle energy domains contending Informational structures, into the quantum-based material world is required. This process is made possible by a phase superposition between resonant bands of subtle energy originating at both sides of the Z.P.E. Such event is accomplished by way of a coupling between biophoton-rich S.E. supplied by the female gamete and resonant similar structures associated to virtual photons transcending the Z.P.E. barrier. Biophotons, just as any photon variants, have - according to recent studies (Firstenber et al., 2013; Georgakopoulos et al., 2018) - an aggregating capacity when certain complex physical conditions are provided.

Nevertheless, basal ultra-weak biophotonic radiation emitted by the egg cell would not reach the critical level able to trigger the photonic bridge in order to fulfill these conditions. A vastly higher, critical intensity threshold is required for this effect.

How such extremal conditions are realized?

The solution of this requirement is found in recently reported studies (Fogel, 2015; Duncan et al., 2016; Que et al., 2014).

A sperm-cell originated metabolic activation signal triggers in the female gamete a short increase in intracellular Ca^{+2} ions, resulting in a "fertilization potential" of the membrane. At the instant of fertilization, a burst of hyperpolarization occurs, with the sudden release of Zn-rich packages from inside the cell. This sudden Zn exocytosis, put in evidence by fluorescent techniques as a breathtaking burst of light, is by now known as the "Zn-spark" - a specific inorganic

signature of the egg activation (see Fig.1). It is consistent with the first intracellular Ca transient initiated at the site of the sperm entry.

Fig. 1. Zinc Spark under fluorescent microscopy

Source: <http://www.sciencefriday.com/articles/picture-of-the-week-zinc-spark>

Ruegg et al. (2018) succeeded to prove that blue light has a control capacity upon DNA into RNA transcription in single cells. His and similar research programs allowed B. E. Mossalam's reporting in his paper (2016) a computational approach to multiplexing genetic and nucleosome positioning codes. The exact positions of nucleosomes play a crucial role in chromatin function. But nucleosome positioning rules can't be explained only by mechanical properties of the base-pair sequencing. Undeformed DNA molecules can be described in two non-vanishing degrees of freedom. But, as we shall see next, to produce a bent DNA molecule in the nucleosome, another degree of non-zero freedom is also required. This is provided by the hyperdimensional geometry the fertilization event is embedded in.

The incoming Self, using its subtle energy envelopes, is triggered to pass the Z.P.E. barrier by the photonic signal emitted by the egg's Zn-spark. The powerful, amplified biphotonic attractor thus supplied as an interdimensional link, gets entangled with the incoming etheric structure bearing the Self's immense informational complexity. This hyperdimensional configuration charged with virtual photons, is able to rich and entangle with its reception pole, starting its modulation task upon the just fertilized zygote from the very instant of conception.

What is the structural proof of this hitherto ignored process, at the biochemical level of the DNA molecule?

Recent research in genetics succeeded to put in evidence a second layer of genetic information on the top of the classical genetic code - namely the topographic parameters of the folding process observed in the DNA strands themselves into nucleosomes (see Fig. 2). This leads to a most specific reading of the coupled base pairs in the double helix. This is an unexpected modulator, originating at the Z.P.E. level primary guiding structure impacting the parental heritage

from outside. At the Z.P.E., reverse entropy is induced in the primary chaotic quantum state dominating the initiation moment of fertilization. Researchers at the Leiden University (Netherlands) confirmed the presence of this second guiding system of genetic instructions.

Fig. 2. Secondary coiling in DNA

Source: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PPMC4845039>

Jeremy England (2008) derived a mathematical formulation indicating that when a group of atoms is driven by an external source of energy, it can gradually restructure itself in order to dissipate increasingly more energy and inexorably acquiring key physical attributes associated with life.

But cognitive and Psi functions have to be also associated with biological life-forms, and this requirement is fulfilled by subtle informational determinants with transcendent origination, which may determine highly specific folding patterns in the DNA strands. This brings into the picture the particular psychologic make-up during the embryogenetic process, which is not protein-dependent. How someone will capitalize his genetically acquire morphologic treats is determined by his/her own transcendental se of personality-related information, enfolded in the folding pattern of the DNA strands.

This paper would be incomplete without mentioning here the reversed process of the Self's re-embodiment, observable at the end of the biological life-span and attentively studied by Slawinsky (1987) and documented in his "death flash" effect. The hitherto close system becomes an open one, The rupture of thermodynamically unstable molecular rings leads to their rearrangement associated to an electronically excited state, the radiative deactivation of which generates the photonic chemiluminescence effect (Slawinsky's "necrotic radiation"). A complex superposition of standing EM waves stored within resonant cavities of biological structures are irreversibly liberated from the system as a coherent integrated field, containing an immense

amount of information. This allows for continuation of consciousness beyond the death of the physical body. Thus, we have a mirror-type symmetry between the photonic mechanisms involved both in the beginning and the end of physical life.

3. Results and discussion

We are at a very early stage in exploring the multiple aspects of the reincarnation process, which due to its highest possible complexity and elusiveness for current instrumental investigation, invites for both a paradigmatic revolution and an expensive development of an adequate technology. The currently available instrumentation and the exploration methodologies they support might be but a starting point for such an adventure requiring heavy funds and most competent experts in the various multidisciplinary domains involved. But the results would be certainly worth of all these joint efforts of open-minded scholars. Some promising starting points are already in place (as I've suggested in my lately published book, *The Reincarnation Process. A Scientific Perspective*).

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